

THE IMPACT OF INTEGRATING SPECIALIZATION MODULES BASED ON THE CLUSTER MODEL ON THE LEARNING PROCESS

Saypillayeva is the daughter of Hilola Barot

Jizzakh State Pedagogical University, teacher of the Department of Distance
Education in Pedagogy-Psychology and Music

Mail address : hsaypillayeva@mail.ru

+998507730775

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14234784>

Annotatsiya. Bugungi kunda oliy ta'lim tizimida ta'lim sifatini oshirish va zamonaviy mehnat bozorining talablariga mos kadrlar tayyorlash masalasi dolzarb ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Ta'lim jarayonida innovatsion usullarni qo'llash orqali o'qitish samaradorligini oshirish, talabalarning bilim va ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish zarurati tug'ilmoqda. Shulardan biri – klaster modeli asosida ixtisoslik modullarini o'qitishdir. Ushbu maqola klaster modelining mohiyati, afzalliklari va uning samaradorligini tahlil qilishga bag'ishlangan.

Kalit so'zlar. Fanlararo integratsiya, klasteri modeli, innovatsion texnologiyalar, kompleks yondashuv, optimaallashtirish, ixtisoslik modullari.

Абстрактный. Сегодня вопрос повышения качества образования и подготовки кадров в соответствии с требованиями современного рынка труда в системе высшего образования приобретает актуальное значение. Существует необходимость повышения эффективности обучения и развития знаний и умений учащихся за счет использования инновационных методов в образовательном процессе. Один из них – обучение модулей специализации на основе кластерной модели. Данная статья посвящена анализу сущности, преимуществ и эффективности кластерной модели.

Ключевые слова. Междисциплинарная интеграция, кластерная модель, инновационные технологии, комплексный подход, оптимизация, модули специализации.

Abstract. Сегодня вопрос повышения качества образования и подготовки кадров в соответствии с требованиями современного рынка труда в системе высшего образования приобретает актуальное значение. Существует необходимость повышения эффективности обучения и развития знаний и умений учащихся за счет использования инновационных методов в образовательном процессе. Один из них – обучение модулей специализации на основе кластерной модели. Данная

статья посвящена анализу сущности, преимуществ и эффективности кластерной модели.

Keywords. Interdisciplinary integration, cluster model, innovative technologies, integrated approach, optimization, specialization modules.

Modular teaching of subject blocks in higher education institutions is based on flexible educational content, educational and learning activities in the organizational and didactic processes of the system, based on the individual capabilities and needs of the student, determining the trajectory of their future professional activity, individual training of the student's social adaptation, personality development. requires the creation of favorable pedagogical conditions in accordance with the curriculum. Pedagogy and psychology specialty modules "Pedagogical technologies", "Methodology of teaching pedagogy and psychology", comparative analysis of the programs of the subjects "Psychological service" implements the goal, which includes the integration of didactic goals, the achievement of each of which is provided by a specific module.

The content of the module is partially structured into learning elements that correspond to didactic objectives, and each learning element should be related to a specific functional element of professional activity. Distinctive features of the teaching of the specified subject module are as follows:

- mandatory study of each component of the didactic system and its visual representation in modular programs and modules;
- providing a clear structure of the educational content, consistent presentation of theoretical material, and a system of monitoring the learning process of didactic materials and knowledge, which allows correcting the educational process;
- variability of teaching, adaptation of the educational process to the individual capabilities and needs of students.

Each module can be mastered independently, and their combination allows to achieve the final goal.

Within the framework of the modules, the theoretical and practical aspects of each type of activity are studied in a complex, synchronous way. This happens by "eliminating" unnecessary theory and redistributing the volume in favor of really necessary theoretical knowledge, which allows the acquisition of competencies, their regulation and systematization, which ultimately leads to an increase in student motivation.

In 1982, a UNESCO conference report defined a module as "a distinct set of learning designed for individual or group learning to focus on a particular skill or group of skills and to progress through self-paced exercises." 'reefed. In technical education, the modular approach is considered as a unit of the learning process that can be learned independently of another system and produces specific know-how or skills. S. Ya. Batsyhev shows that "a module is a part of a block, a volume of educational material that ensures the initial acquisition of certain theoretical and practical skills for performing any concrete work . "

Despite the many existing definitions of the module, in our opinion, they can all be systematized according to three aspects:

as a unit of the state curriculum for a specialty representing a set of academic subjects that meet the requirements of qualification descriptions;

as an organizational-methodical interdisciplinary structure representing a set of subjects (sections) from various academic subjects necessary for mastering one specialty and providing interdisciplinary connections of the educational process;

as an organizational-methodical structural unit of one academic subject.

In modular education, a student's relatively independent work on mastering an individual program consisting of individual modules (modular units) is considered. Each module represents a complete professional movement, the development of which continues through step-by-step operations. In modular training, the possibility of step-by-step training is created through fully reduced and in-depth classification of training programs, that is, it becomes possible to individualize training. The following goals are aimed at the transition to modular training:

- ensuring the continuity of education;
- individualization of teaching;
- to create sufficient conditions for independent learning of educational material;
- acceleration of training;
- achieving effective mastery of science.

Modular teaching requires the delivery of problem-based and guided lectures that provide general information on the main issues of the subject. Lectures should focus on the development of students' creative abilities. The module should be made up of practical and laboratory exercises, lectures, and they should be supplemented with new material to study the content of the lectures.

In the teaching of specialized modules in higher education, it is necessary to ensure coherence between the modules of the subject, to speed up teaching, to

regularly monitor and evaluate students' knowledge, to teach practical activities based on interest, and to teach the subject through step-by-step teaching of the educational material. effective absorption is achieved.

In the process of education, social experience is gained and an emotional and value-based attitude to reality is formed. The concept of "modular education" was formed in the late 60s. In the 20th century, it appeared in the United States as an alternative to traditional education, incorporating many advanced ideas gathered in pedagogical theory and practice.

The interest of different researchers in modular education is determined by the desire to achieve different goals. In order to increase the efficiency of teaching specialized modules in higher education, the researches of our country's scientists NXAvliyokulov and KTO Olimov on the stages of pedagogical technology design and the development of modular teaching principles, J.G. Yoldoshev is dedicated to clarifying the general foundations of current pedagogical technologies. studies, candidate theses of MIDaminov , S. Yu. Ashurova on modular teaching technologies can be cited as an example.

In education, a module is a relatively integrated structural unit of information, activity, process or organizational-methodical structure.

Inside the module, as a purposeful functional unit, the content and technology of its mastery are integrated into a system of high-level integrity. Therefore, it can be considered an individualized curriculum in terms of method, level of independence and pace.

A modular structure consists of interconnected system elements that have "inputs and outputs" to supersystems and subsystems. The main characteristics of the module are relative completeness, normalization, autonomy, continuity and can be variably combined with other modules.

Education is the main way of learning, the process of acquiring knowledge, skills and abilities under the guidance of teachers, master trainers and others.

Modern researcher PAYusyavichene defines a module as "a unit of logically completed educational material, a program of targeted actions and a block of information containing methodical guidance, which ensures the achievement of the set didactic goals."

The authors of this research aim to provide flexibility in the teaching content, to create the most favorable conditions for personal development in cognitive activity in accordance with the individual curriculum by adapting the education to the individual needs of the person and his basic training level. they see Modular teaching absorbed the dynamics of development of modern didactic

theories and synthesized their features, which made it possible to more successfully combine different approaches to the methods of choosing content, presenting it and organizing the educational process. This shows the continuity of modular education with other theories and concepts of education [4].

The effectiveness of teaching specialization modules in higher education depends on the quality of the modular programs and modules that make up the course program, as well as the combination of complex, integrated and specific goals. When creating a training program for specialized modules, it is necessary to take into account the logic of formation of the content of each module and the schedule of training sessions. The textbook is used as the main element of the content of the cognitive part of the educational module, the information in it is compiled in the form of a map, the topic of the lesson, the page in the textbook where this material is located, and the test questions that the student must answer when mastering the educational material are shown.

The content of the pedagogical series of subjects or educational modules taught in HEIs is based on existing legal and regulatory frameworks, legislative requirements, advanced educational technologies, including information and communication technologies. and introduction to the latest achievements in applied research, technological development and modern methods of organizing the educational process will serve to increase the effectiveness of the educational process.

The article talks about the organization of modular training on problematic and guided lectures, which provide generalized information on the main issues of science, and the effectiveness of training of specialty modules.

References:

1. Uzbekistan Republic President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev . It is intended for 2022-2026 New of Uzbekistan development strategy Decree No. PF-60 of 2022.
2. H. Saypillayeva . // SCIENCE IS A SOCIETY Scientific method log // top in education specialty modules teaching efficiency increase technologies - 2024, No. 1/2, pp. 72-73.
3. HS Aypillayeva . // American Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development // Didactic opportunities of integration in the
4. content of specialty modules - page 11, 2024 .
5. HS Aypillayeva . // VOCATIONAL EDUCATION // Specialization modules in teaching individual education principles application - No. 2, 2024, p. 87.
6. Yutsvavichene P. Theory and practice of modular training. / P. Yutsvavichene . - Kaunas: Shviesa , 1989. - 272 p.

POLAND

CURRENT APPROACHES AND NEW RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCES

International scientific-online conference

POLAND

7. Avliyokulov N.Kh. Module system of teaching and practical foundations of pedagogical technology. - Bukhara. Author, 2001
8. Olimov Q.T. Pedagogical technologies. - T.: "Science and technologies" publishing house, 2011. - 275 p.
9. Yoldoshev J.G'. and Polatov Sh.P., Organization of methodological service in education based on innovative technologies, educational and methodological manual, Tashkent - "Modern education" - 2011, 165.
10. Daminov M.I., Analysis and essence of using modular technology in education. Pedagogical skill - Bukhara, 2007. #1- B-11-14.
11. Ashyrova S.Yu. Scientific-methodical bases of modular study of special subjects. Diss... ped.f.n. -T.: 2005 .-180 p.